

The Relativity hidden in Quantum Phenomena

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Abstract:

This article aims to reinterpret the hidden principle and mechanism of the double-slit experiment in a more comprehensible manner, and to demonstrate a new perspective that better clarifies existent phenomena. This new perspective involves conducting the observation and analysis at a relative angle, which can partially reconcile the divergence between the quantum theory and the relativity theory. Several concepts are redefined from a relative viewpoint. In the proposed interpretation, the wave-particle duality observed in typical double-slit experiments gives only a surface appearance of certainty. The non-locality hidden in special relativity theory, which can also be found from a relative viewpoint, can subsequently be used to explain weird quantum behaviors, as well as other classic theories like principle of least action. The considerations on concept of relativity are applicable to other cosmological phenomena such as dark energy, dark matter, gravity and curvature, providing a more comprehensible explanation than conventional thinking. A series of other doubtful phenomena, such as the nature of inertia or the probability of quantum events, can also be reasonably comprehended in light of the present conclusions. And finally, possible application directions are cautiously forecasted.

Keywords:

Quantum Theory; Relativity Theory; Double-slit experiment; Wave-particle duality; Dark energy; Curvature

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1. Introduction:

1.1. Doubts in the double-slit experiment

The distinguished Dr. Richard Feynman once told us, “The double-slit experiment has in it the heart of quantum mechanics, contains the only mystery of quantum mechanics.”

Most of the double-slit experiments can be subsumed into the following categories:

(1) Original version

(2) Individual particles version

(3) “Which-way” version

(4) Delayed choice version

(5) Quantum eraser version

(6) Weak measurement version

(7) Other versions

Nearly all of the double-slit experiment results are characterized by irrationality, unpredictability, non-objectivity, anti-commonsense, or a combination of these.

To explain the above experimental results, researchers have turned to strange quantum behavior, phenomena displayed during the experiment, and most importantly, the mechanism behind these results. Various interpretations [1-7] prevailed once, or to this day.

Most of previous interpretations are imperfect. Resolving these imperfections is the strength of this article. Details of the article's contributions are listed in Table 1.

	Previous interpretation	Strength of the article
Characteristic of matter	Using concept of wave-particle duality to interpret is difficult to be comprehended.	Using concept of certainty to interpret is easier to be comprehended.
Special relativity	Locality will be treated as its essential property, which will cause irreconcilable contradiction with quantum behaviors.	The non-locality hidden in special relativity theory could be found with a relevant point of view, and will be used to explain weird behaviors shown by quantum.
Cosmology phenomena	Treating some phenomena in an absolute perspective, will cause incomprehensible results.	When similar thought of relativity applied, it will give a more comprehensible explanation.
Probability of quantum	Some basic and foundational characteristics of quantum still pending without an comprehensible explanation.	A series of doubts like probability of quantum will have a reasonable answer after deductions step by step.

Table 1. Contributions of the present study

1.2. Redefined concepts

To better explain the perspectives on the double-slit experiments, several concepts must be clarified beforehand:

(1) Observation

Normally Measurements is broadly classified as quantum or classical. Here a more general measurement (or observation) will be defined.

An observed system does not necessarily interact with any laboratory device or instrument located in the observing system. When one system is interacting with outer system, to exchange information with outer system, in other words, to induce relevance, it means the observation has occurred.

The interaction form can be attraction by gravity, projection by photons, touching by hand, glancing by a naked eye, or blocking by a barrier (Fig. 1). Regardless of its type, an interaction means that an observation has occurred.

Depending on the quantity of information acquired from the observed system, observations can be slight, normal, or complete, although these divisions are

qualitative with no hard boundaries.

A slight observation acquires minor information that could be limited to one dimension, one degree of freedom of motion, or even less. In contrast, a complete observation obtains nearly all of the contained information, and the observed system becomes part of the observing system. A normal observation acquires partial information, the degree of which is between the above two.

In summary, the observation of objects, behaviors, or phenomena is the process of acquiring and receiving information from the observed system by a relative observing system.

Another kind of interaction will erase relevant information from the outer system, in other words, will reduce the relevance between two systems. Moreover, an interaction that neither acquires nor erases relevant information is also possible.

(2) Certainty

This concept is more widely known as wave-particle duality, which is not the most explicit way to describe object traits. The macroscopic world is composed of microscopic objects, which comparatively possess more fundamental properties.

However, as humans live in the macroscopic world, they naturally view the macroscopic world as more objective than the microscopic world. From daily experience, humans perceive particles as solid objects like balls, and waves as oscillating entities like disturbed water.

If these two concepts are comprehended to underlie a more fundamental concept, doubts will surely arise. To alleviate the contradictions, we must temporarily forego our familiarity with the macroscopic world, and guide our thinking towards the more fundamental microscopic world.

Microscopic objects, which constitute the macroscopic world, possess the following properties:

A) They can evolve smoothly when isolated from the outer system. Unless observed, they are normally

invisible to the outer system.

B) When observed by an outer system, they will be connected, linked, cohered, or entangled with the outer system, meaning that they can impart their information (slightly, completely or partially) to the outer system.

C) The behavioral traits of an observed microscopic object depend on the degree of observation. More observations will acquire more information, and will increase the certainty of the observed behavior. Each state can be represented by a wave function.

D) An observation is an interaction that links a microscopic object to the outer system. As this link is strengthened, the behavior becomes more certain (more particle-like). An example is the strong force between the atoms in iron ball. Weaker links, such as the forces between H₂O molecules in water, cause more uncertain (wave-like) behaviors.

The above description is consistent with the Copenhagen interpretation to some extent [8], but helps to intuit the quantum behavior shown in the double-slit experiment.

Certainty depends not on whether the behavior is macroscopic or microscopic, or whether the entity is classical or quantum, but on the difficulty level of interacting (exchanging information) with the outer system; in other words, on its ability to induce relevance.

Macroscopic objects and classical systems keep on exposing excessive information to the outer system; consequently, our daily observable world is tightly linked into a highly undivided and certain one by these information exposures.

On the contrary, microscopic objects and quantum systems are easily isolated from other systems, either partially or nearly completely; accordingly, they easily show uncertainty in experiments.

In summary, the certainty of objects, behaviors, or phenomena is directly related to the quantity of information obtained by the observing system from the observed system

(3) Existence

The concept of existence straddles the boundary between Science and Philosophy. Hence, this concept should be described more rigorously. The existence of objects, behaviors or phenomena should be relative (see Fig. 2).

An existing system should interact with the outer system, exchange information with it, and induce relevance (i.e., become observable). More rigorously, the observed system exists relative to the outer system.

If a system has no interaction with the outer system, no information exchanged, no relevance induced and not observable, it means the system is not existent relative to the outer system. However, the aforesaid non-observability of a system does not disqualify its existence. Each system exists relative to itself.

In some special circumstances, we can say that a system exists relative to an outer system that differs from our daily world.

(4) Objectivity

This is another concept approaching Philosophy, and is synonymous with authenticity. Also more rigorously, the objectivity of objects, behaviors, or phenomena should be relative.

In our daily experience, the observable world or universe is united into an objective whole. The criterion that this “whole” is the most and the only objective one, is often applied to verify the objectivity of other objects or systems. One viewpoint can reach a seemingly correct conclusion, but not a sufficiently objective conclusion. Another viewpoint may yield a different perception of the situation.

Just like in above content, different conclusions about the phenomenon “whether the system is existent”, can be reached when a system is observed by different outer systems. Relativity can perfect the definition of objectivity.

All of the above concepts needed to be redefined. Such a large number of relative concepts necessitate the recall of another fundamental theory, which is detailed in the following contents.

2. Methods and results:

Reinterpretation of the double-slit experiment

We now provide an explanation of the experiments in the above categories. As specific experiments in each category show similar features, only one representative experiment is discussed from each category.

(1) Original version

The results of the original double-split experiment, obtained by Thomas Young in 1801, can be well explained by either classical or quantum theory. Therefore, they are not repeated here.

(2) Individual particle version [9]

In this version of the double-split experiment, a single particle exhibits wave-like behavior, seemingly passing through both slits in the same time before self-interacting. However, it appears as a single light point on the screen, revealing particle-like behavior. As further information is gathered, an interference pattern forms on the screen by numerous single points, as shown in Fig. 3.

In the Copenhagen interpretation, this phenomenon is described by the well-known complementarity principle [8]: “A particular experiment can demonstrate particle or wave property, but not both at the same time.” In fact, the Copenhagen interpretation is merely a surface interpretation. A more comprehensible interpretation is proposed below.

When a microscopic object passes through two slits, its path information is lost, and is not easily regained by the outer system, due to its limited size and limited method can be used to acquire its path information. Therefore, the particle can only exhibit uncertain (wave-like) behavior.

When the microscopic object interacts with the screen, the lost information returns, so the behavior becomes certain (particle-like).

The interference pattern on the screen behind the slits is just a type of shadow representing the certainty degree of the microscopic objects conveyed to the

outer system. It also represents the amount of information imparted to the outer system by the microscopic objects; in other words, how much information of the microscopic objects is known to the outer system.

To clarify this statement, I represent our outer system as a computer that can adequately compute and draw a well-defined picture, provided that enough input data are supplied.

If very limited information is inputted, but the computer is still compelled to finish the drawing, the output will be the best that can be achieved under the preconditions (see Fig. 4), only a vague one. With the same principle, our outer system also produces a similarly vague output when limited information is supplied.

In both scenarios, the output data can provide only an approximate and uncertain picture. The computer and the outer system, they are both cheated, due to lack in input data. In the absence of sufficient information and with no alternative solution, a system can only compromise, to show a vague picture.

Note that when the path information in the double-slit experiment is restored, single particles gradually compose an interference pattern on the screen. Interference between the split paths seemingly occurs despite in a compromised picture. That is, having accepted the uncertainty, our system also accepts the consequences.

Such uncertainty leads to two consequences: splitting into two parts, and self-interaction of the two parts. Only the second consequence remains, meaning that only this kind of interaction during the uncertain period remains.

In this version of the double-split experiment, we conclude that our outer system, which can be generalized to the scope of the known universe, will in special case admit the following phenomenon:

If one system exposes only limited information to other systems, the behavior which showed in other systems will be presented in an uncertain way.

The less information exposed, the more uncertain behavior presented, and vice versa.

If this kind of uncertainty unavoidably causes interactions among the different uncertain states, then the interaction effect remains after the uncertainty is removed.

(3) “Which-way” version [10]

In this version of the double-split experiment, the particle seemingly passes through both slits at the same time. None of these experiments can detect the specific path of the particle without disturbing its wave-like behavior (see Fig. 5).

The complementarity principle in the Copenhagen interpretation [8] can explain this behavior, but this article proposes another explanation that will be better accepted by proponents of relativity theory.

Special relativity theory [15] posits that “the laws of physics are invariant (i.e. identical) in all inertial (i.e. non-accelerating) frames of reference.”

A microscopic particle moves relative to the outer system at light or near-light speed, along a path that can be described as a wave function. This is the conclusion from our observation angle.

Let us suppose that the particle itself can also observe, think, analyze, and conclude. The particle views the outer system moving relative to itself, at light, or near-light speed, along a path that can be described by a wave function. The wave functions of the observer and particle will probably coincide.

In the wave function description, the two slits will partially merge. The merged part will be the most possible path along which the particle is compelled to move. Here, the manner of selection was not an issue, because there is no other choice for the particle at all.

If the particle ponders which slit it exited, it will find no answer, because it received insufficient information from the outer system. In its own view, the outer system also behaves in an uncertain way.

How can we know whether the particle divided when it passed through the slits? How it determined its final path? What happened during that period? And

what is the truth? The most suitable answer depends on our observation system. If viewed in the outer system, the particle split, behaved like a wave and passed through both slits simultaneously, it will self-interfere and eventually hit the screen. The splitting effect disappears but the interference effect remains.

If viewed within the system of the particle, the particle always remain stationary without splitting, behaving like a real particle. The channel approaching the particle, appears to be a mixture of two slits exhibiting wave-like behavior, and the wave-behaved screen appears to self-interfere as it approaches the particle. When the path information returns (at the time of the screen hitting the particle), the past path of the screen is observed to be nonlinear, and the light point is deflected from the screen center. Occasionally, this deflection composes an interference pattern, together with other previous deflections observed by other previous particles.

Through these transformations of the observation systems or reference frames, the particle will find these answers:

First, it cannot split because in its own reference frame, it exists as a pure particle with 100% certainty.

Second, it cannot choose a path, because in its own reference frame there is no other choice. All what it can do is remaining stationary.

Finally, it cannot know what happened during that period, because the outer system also behaved vaguely due to lack of information available for particle to analyze.

This is the truth given by particle, observed from its own angle. The differences between a human observer and the particle observer are shown in Fig. 6.

In this version of the double-slit experiment, we conclude that:

If one system lacks sufficient information of another system, and observes it in an uncertain way, the second system will observe the first system with an equal degree of uncertainty.

The uncertainty described by a wave function should be invariant in any inertial reference frame.

The lack of information between different observing systems influences how the truth is concluded, but the uncertainty is always true.

The above mentioned details do not violate any of the cornerstone of current quantum theory, but are more comprehensible and more compatible with other theories.

(4) Delayed choice version [11]

The most famous delayed choice version is Wheeler's delayed choice experiment (Fig. 7). When a second splitter is inserted, one light is always on, but when the second splitter is removed, the two lights are alternately on. Because the photon encounters the second splitter after choosing its path through the first splitter, it seems that a delayed choice at the second splitter is made to decide what happens at the first splitter.

Actually, with previous conclusion, we can find irrespective of the second splitter being inserted, a photon takes two paths through the first splitter, and exhibits wave-like behavior. If the second splitter is inserted, the two paths interact before hitting the detector, so the effect of the interaction remains, and one light is always on. If the second splitter is removed, no interaction occurs, so the two lights are alternatively and randomly on.

This delayed choice version didn't show real delayed choice features. But we can find other feature more interesting, i.e. human consciousness participation from it. In this version a human consciousness was making choice, to interact with surrounding circumstances and to cause consequences. This process is similar with what we do in daily lives.

In the delayed choice version, we can imagine replacing human decision-making method with another decision-making method, as proposed by Dr. Schrödinger in his thought experiment. For example, reconsider it as a radioactive source with a decaying probability, and introduce a relevant detector, counter, controller, and actuator. Let the actuator be triggered

by some minimal quantity of detected radioactive particles within a certain period, called the threshold level. Once triggered, the actuator inserts the second beam splitter into the path.

The probability of decay, the threshold level, the trigger logic of the actuator, and other factors can be preset and controlled. Similarly, a participant in this experiment can be instructed to operate the equipment in various ways: totally randomly, pseudo-randomly following some rule, or deterministically.

This alternative experiment will obtain the same results as the original one. And which experiment is governed by human consciousness is difficult to discern from the experimental results.

In this version of the double-slit experiment, we conclude the following:

Human consciousness in daily life behaves similarly to a quantum system. Different pre-controlled methods will yield a random result, a definite result, or a result that can be predicted with a certain probability.

(5) Quantum eraser version [12]

The quantum eraser version of the double-split experiment marks the path information, and interference pattern disappears. When the path information is erased, the pattern reappears. This behavior mimics a quantum game of hide-and-seek (Fig. 8).

As described above, the interference pattern shown on the screen is just a type of shadow representing the certainty with which the microscopic objects are shown to the outer system.

As the path information is erased, the object exhibits wave-like behavior in the aspect of path and inevitably establishes an interference pattern. When marked, the path information returns, along with the particle-like behavior.

This version of the double-slit experiment implies that:

Path information, which is generalizable to any aspect of information, can be erased or marked

repeatedly.

Information erasure induces uncertainty, and information remarking restores the certainty (Fig. 9).

When every aspect of information is erased, the object can be rendered invisible.

(6) Weak measurement version [13]

This version of the double-slit experiment is characterized by very limited observations that impact only slightly on the interference pattern. Meanwhile, the particle path information is almost fully determined. The particle- and wave-like behaviors can seemingly appear simultaneously.

Actually it is the same situation described in previous content by the slight observation mechanism. Also as described above, the interference pattern appearing on the screen is just a type of shadow representing the certainty extent of the microscopic objects shown to the outer system (Fig. 10).

As more information is displayed, the results become more certain. There are not only two absolute states. The actual state can be intermediate between a particle and a wave, based on the amount of certainty acquired.

In this version of the double-slit experiment, we conclude that:

If very limited observation (i.e. slight observation) is presented, to the extent that the interference pattern is only slightly affected, particle-like and wave-like behaviors seem to appear simultaneously. However, neither of them is 100% pure. The real state of the observed object is intermediate between a wave and a particle.

There is no absolute wave and no absolute particle. Only certainty is absolute.

As repeatedly stated, the interference pattern is just a type of shadow, like tree shadows on the ground. When the wind rustles the tree, the shadow moves by an amount that depends on the wind magnitude. More the wind, more the movement of shadow. It may lead

us to consider that the wind interacts with the shadow. But essentially, the wind interacts with the tree, not the shadow.

The wind, tree, and ground are analogous to an observation, the observed system, and the observing system, respectively. The moving and stationary behavior of tree exhibit particle-like (more certain) and wave-like (less certain) behavior, respectively. Moreover, the stationary shadow is the pattern, and the moving direction is the path.

When the wind is minimal, the shadow is almost stationary. As the wind power increases, the shadow begins a slight leftward or rightward movement. We may conclude that in a weak wind, the movement direction of the shadow seems discernable, although the shadow remains almost stationary. This situation describes the inherent nature of weak measurement.

We may also conclude that the wind cannot induce a strong unidirectional movement of the tree while keeping it stationary. This situation embodies the complementarity principle.

We should also be aware of that the essence is the interaction between wind and tree. The shadow is only an ordinary appearance. Persisting on try to acquire the moving shadow (path) and stationary shadow (pattern) at the same time is not necessary.

(7) Other versions [14]

Many other versions of the double-split experiment have been developed. Among these alternative versions, we visit the version of Kim et al. [14] reported in 2000.

I personally admire this version, as it embodies all of the above-mentioned elements: individual particles, the “which-way” concept, delayed choice, quantum erasure, and weak measurement. Most of the elements were elaborated in the above contents. Only delayed choice will be further explored here.

The most intriguing aspect of this version is that “the information of a quantum can be erased or marked even after registration of its entangled twin”. This unbelievable behavior demands an acceptable explanation.

The following basic principles of special relativity theory [15] have been proven many times, and their correctness need not be questioned:

“Two events, simultaneous for one observer, may not be simultaneous for another observer if the observers are in relative motion.”

“Moving clocks are measured to tick more slowly than an observer's ‘stationary’ clock.”

“Objects are measured to be shortened in the direction that they are moving with respect to the observer.”

These three principles provide the answer without requiring calculation:

The photon moves at light speed relative to our experimental system. In the photon's frame of reference, our system shrinks to zero length in the moving direction, and our time is frozen. Every time the photon changes direction in its optical path, our system shrinks to zero length in the new moving direction accordingly.

Light reflection differs from acceleration, and does not warrant a discussion of general relativity theory.

In its own reference frame, the photon will travel from its source to a detector in zero time, because there is no distance to spend time. Meanwhile, its entangled twin will hit another detector in the same zero time.

When measured in Minkowski space, the space-time distance between each point along the photon route is zero. Therefore, all behaviors occur at the same time and same place, so all information is instantaneously acquired.

Returning to the experimental process, the following are observed (see Fig. 11):

The photon passes through two slits, gets refracted or reflected several times and hits detector D_1 (or D_2), simultaneously. Furthermore, at the same time, its entangled twins meet each other at D_0 , and their interaction forms an interference pattern.

The photon can also pass through two slits, be refracted or reflected several times, hit detector D_3 (or

D_4), regain the lost information, and confirm its previous two-slit path to a single path, simultaneously. Furthermore, at the same time, because its path information has been retrieved, when the entangled twins meet at D_0 , only one of them remains and no interference pattern is formed.

Following from the above explanation, we can naturally consider that:

If the particle is not a photon, but a particle with measurable mass and lower speed, what will happen? If simultaneous process really happens, what are the causes for non-simultaneous processes observed by us? If different observers reach different conclusions, what is the truth?

These questions lead us to the most untouchable fundamental law, namely, the law of causality. Interpretations must be cautiously made.

First, entities other than photons, such as fields and causality itself, are transmitted at the velocity of light relative to any observing system, and will exert the same effect as photons. When causality travels at light velocity relative to us, it cannot spend any finite time at any point in space either.

Second, it is still because of relativity. In the view of causality (suppose it has), it finishes its entire job instantaneously. But in our sight, it only finishes the job at light speed.

Finally, there is no absolute truth, only absolute relativity.

In this version of the double-slit experiment, we conclude the following:

The eigenvalue of the state of one object, behavior, phenomenon, or system can be 100% accurately observed only by itself.

Any observing system with relative motion or relative uncertainty to the observed system will reach a discrepant conclusion.

Once the eigenvalue is established, the causality will be transmitted instantaneously, but the effect will be revealed to other observers only at light speed.

In the following contents, I will consider an extended version of the thought experiment that is based on Kim et al.'s version [14], along with wider considerations.

3. Discussion:

Explanations of relevant typical phenomena

With the above definitions and conclusions derived from various double-slit experiments, we can re-evaluate other dilemmas, phenomena, and doubts.

(1) Schrödinger's cat

This thought experiment is easily explained. A cat is enclosed in a box with trace amounts of a radioactive substance. If the substance decays, it triggers a Geiger counter, and an actuator knocks a hammer onto a vial of poison. If the substance does not decay, the vial is not broken and the cat survives. The cat seems in the superposition of life and death, as microscopic objects usually behaved.

Actually some relevant information is unavoidably exposed, although not observable to an observer outside the box.

The detector knows the status of the radioactive source, the actuator knows the status of the detector, the hammer knows the status of the actuator, and the vial knows the status of the hammer. Even the ground can feel whether the cat is walking or lying down for several days.

If the cat belongs to the observed system and all other entities belong to the observing system, the status of the cat is immediately confirmed. If the human outside box belongs to the observing system and all other entities belong to the observed system, the status of the cat is a real superposition of states.

After these explanation, we can think deeper. Suppose that we replace the radioactive source system with a tiger, or a human armed with a knife. The status of the cat may be different from the original thought experiment; however, it still cannot be known to the observer outside the box.

The decay probability of the radioactive source

(50%) is fixed. The behaviors of the human and tiger will be unpredictable and random. These two kinds of system seems different. But if we design, build, and continually update a complicated quantum system throughout a time period as long as the life of a tiger or a human, then the probability of an event in this quantum system can also be set to an unpredictable level.

In the contrary, if we enforce specific and strict training rules on the human or tiger, we can control the probability of their certain behavior.

As a simple daily life example, suppose that you are returning home from work. Your wife has instructed you to prepare lunch for your daughter, provided that your daughter has returned home from school. You surely wish to know whether your daughter is at home. Suppose too that your cellphone has run out of battery power. How do you determine that? Perhaps relevant information has been acquired by the TV controller in her hand, or the sofa beneath her body, but it is unavailable to you.

You remember that your daughter likes only fish, but you like mutton. With a limited amount of money, the best choice is to purchase less than usual quantities of both foods.

When you arrive home, you find that your daughter is not at home. The uncertainty has become a certainty, but the fish cannot be returned to the place of purchase.

This real-life example is very similar to the phenomenon of the double-slit experiment.

Before a choice is made, it is unknown to other parties. Once the choice is made, it is known to others only if shared or interacted with the surrounding circumstances. Once the choice made and enacted, its effect will become obvious to others. If the indecisiveness is maintained, the future expectations remain obscure, and unpredictable outcomes can ensue.

From the above description, we conclude that:

In the macroscopic world, superposition states can occur when an observer cannot acquire the relevant

information from the observed system.

The driving mechanism of conscious decisions is similar to that of quantum decision making, or at least exerts a similar effect.

(2) Einstein–Podolsky–Rosen (EPR) paradox [16]

The EPR paradox is also well known. Simplistically judging whether Einstein or Bohr is correct would be reckless. Instead, the judgement should be based on the above definitions and conclusions.

The most controversial part of the EPR paradox is the two principles: the principle of locality and the principle of realism.

A) The principle of locality can be explained by a previous conclusion: Once the eigenvalue of a particle is established, the causality is instantaneously transmitted to its twin particle.

In this experiment, although the two particles are separated by a large distance, this distance shrinks to zero when the causality is transmitted at light speed. Any newly received effect on one particle is instantaneously transmitted to the other particle.

Although this experiment violates the principle of locality, it does not make Einstein lose. I believe that Einstein's original purpose was not to verify the principle of locality. He was trying to create a paradox, which is deduced from the Quantum Theory and not compatible with an already existing truth. Principle of locality is only the presupposed "truth". His original purpose was to uphold the principle of realism.

B) The principle of realism can also be explained by a previous conclusion: The eigenvalue of the state of one object, behavior, phenomenon, or system can only be wholly and accurately observed by itself. Any other observing system with a relative motion or relative uncertainty to the observed system will reach a discrepant conclusion.

That is, realism does exist, but can be observed only by the object, behavior, phenomenon, or system generating the realism. An outside observer will obtain a result similar to the original eigenvalue, but not identical to it. In one words, realism is relative.

In addition, the aforesaid realism is limited to states that make sense without comparison to other systems. States such as velocity or position can be sensibly discussed only when compared with other systems.

Let us discuss the events in this experiment. Two entangled particles are created, isolated, and separated by a large distance (Fig. 12). Initially, the states of both particles are opposite and fixed at the moment of creation of the particles. Thereafter, the states remain unchanged or can evolve internally in some special cases, but always remain opposite.

Once observed, the status of a particle is revealed to us, and the particle disentangles from its partner. Moreover, the isolation is broken and the internal evolution ends. The unobserved particle retains its opposite status at the moment of observation, and if found at a later time, its state will oppose that of the previously observed particle.

Although this explanation differs from the wave function collapse principle, it demonstrates the same result while being acceptable to opponents of wave function collapse. There is no collapse. The states are already there. This explanation truly resembles with collapse theory, because only when the moment of "collapse", can we obtain the required information.

The above description does not include the interaction between two separated particles; however, it does not deny the existence of such interactions. Moreover, even if interactions between separated particles exists, it doesn't disprove Einstein's understanding of realism. Einstein realized a part of the true meaning of realism, but attempted to prove it using an unsuitable compared truth.

Wave function collapse is only a surface phenomenon, but does not undermine Bohr's work. Bohr regarded an observed behavior that can be acquired and most closely resembles realism, as realism itself. This judgement is difficult to assess as right or wrong, but his thoughts on the weakness of the EPR paradox were accurate.

In this duel between Bohr and Einstein, the score is therefore tied. Both relativity theory and quantum theory are correct, and cooperate tightly to weave a

marvelous story for us.

Interaction between distant particles, not revealed obviously in previous discussion, is a real phenomenon, and is called entanglement.

Entanglement satisfies the sufficiency condition because causality can be transmitted instantaneously, and the necessity condition because the two particles are isolated from an outer system (to a large extent in certain aspects). During its evolution, a particle will more plausibly interact with its entangled twin than with the outer system.

Once entanglement is established, the states of the twin particles remain fixed or change simultaneously. Being in opposite states is not the only way when entanglement is established. But due to the generation of entanglement via decaying or spontaneous parametric down-conversion (SPDC), is more achievable today, which always produces opposite-state particle pairs, it looks like entanglement always demonstrated in opposite states.

When one entangled particle is observed, it detaches from its partner and established a new entanglement with the observing system. The detaching or disbanding phenomenon is called *decoherence*. The two particles separately maintain their states determined at the moment of the first observation, and appear to interact over a distance.

If another interaction occurs prior to observation, which changes the status of one particle without acquiring any information, the states of both particles will change and the entanglement remains. As there are no other interactions, the consequences of the change are instantly transmitted only to the twin in the same isolated system, and are revealed to us at light speed. In this way, real interactions can occur between separated and distant particles.

From the above description, we conclude that the interactions between systems can be divided into three categories:

Observation: An observation transfers relevant information from the observed system to the observing

system, thereby increasing the certainty of conveyed behavior of the observed system to the observing system. An observation causes decoherence from the observed system and entanglement with the observing system.

Omission: An omission eliminates relevant information of the observed system from the observing system, thereby decreasing the certainty of the behavior conveyed by the observed system to the observing system. An omission causes decoherence from the observing system.

Operation: An operation only changes the state of the observed system; the relevant information in the observing system neither increases nor decreases. An operation causes an interaction between two distant particles.

(3) Bell's inequality [17]

This one is an unavertable challenge. Many versions of verification have been conducted to attempt to test it. Its core idea is to determine the existence of the hidden variable theory.

Obviously, local hidden-variable theory cannot be established because the causality is transmitted instantaneously. Can there exist a non-local hidden-variable theory?

Relative light speed motions can be observed in any system, so non-locality is already embedded in special relativity theory [15]. Moreover, as the laws of physics are invariant in different systems, special relativity theory [15] can assist our understanding of uncertainty, objectivity, realism, and other quantum phenomena.

We thus conclude that:

Special relativity theory is among the best candidates of non-local hidden-variable theory.

The key always lay in Einstein's pocket; however, it appears that he never intended to apply his theory to non-local hidden variable theory, possibly to avoid any assistance to the quantum theory, again.

(4) Entropy

In previous sections, information, this term has been

frequently mentioned. In physics, information is formally defined as *entropy*. The two mainly modern usages of entropy are in thermodynamics and informatics.

In thermodynamics, entropy expresses the second law of thermodynamics, which also represents the unidirectional time arrow. In informatics, it expresses the uncertainty in the expected results, which can be reduced by acquiring relevant information.

Actually some relations between the two usages can be concluded:

The information entropy is part of the whole entropy in an object or event. The more proportion of information entropy is, the more uncertainty the object or event shows.

Information entropy is reduced by acquiring information, either by observation or performing work. The more knowledge of the object or an event, the less uncertainty it shows.

When the information entropy proportion falls to zero, all information of the object is known. Conversely, when this proportion equals one, the object or event is completely unknown.

Whenever the information entropy is reduced by observation, new information entropy is generated. Therefore, the proportion of information entropy can never equal zero in practice. This is the inner nature of uncertainty principle.

The three above-summarized interactions between systems can now be checked in terms of entropy.

Omission: An omission increases the uncertainty, and therefore the whole entropy of the observed system. This result is consistent with the second law of thermodynamics.

Operation: An operation interacts with the observed system without doing work. The uncertainty and entropy are not reduced, and the second law of thermodynamics is not violated.

Observation: An observation does work on the observed system, reducing the uncertainty and the entropy, again without violating the second law of thermodynamics.

The uncertainty (information entropy) will not reduce automatically. Only when observation is proceeded, which means work is performed, will it reduce. Therefore, the quantum behaviors shown in previous experiments do not violate the second law of thermodynamics.

Reducing and increasing the proportion of information entropy will enhance and reduce the visibility of an object or behavior, respectively. The wave function can be considered as one approach to depict it.

(5) Black holes

Macroscopic objects contain large quantity of entropy, implying large quantity of information to be acquired, and also abundant methods enabling us to acquire them. Microscopic objects possess few quantity of entropy, implying few quantity of information to be acquired, and also very limited methods left for us to acquire them.

Different proportions of already acquired information among the total information introduce different degrees of certainty. The non-acquired part is the above-mentioned information entropy.

The Universe contains one kind of peculiar object with exceptionally huge quantities of entropy which can be acquired by very few observation methods. These objects are called black holes.

The total entropy of a black hole is not lost, but is perfectly hidden behind the event horizon. Therefore, a black hole does not violate the second law of thermodynamics. The huge quantity of entropy can be estimated from the area of a sphere, but the nature of the information cannot be known, which makes the black holes remain highly uncertain. Of course, if we only consider mass, electric charge or angular momentum as the total information that we need to acquire, then the black hole is pretty certain.

The most incomprehensible part of a black hole is its singularity. The infinitely large mass density caused by an infinitely small volume is intractable in calculations,

but can be managed by the uncertainty principle.

In the microscopic world, the uncertainty principle is needed because microscopic systems react largely to disturbance (i.e. observation). In macroscopic objects with large mass, small disturbances exert negligible effect. The huge mass of a singularity will show extremely minor uncertainties in disturbance (i.e. observation). However, any uncertainty, no matter how minor, will produce a finite result. Accordingly, a singularity will quiver in an extremely narrow space. This movement will be described as a probability function that is almost entirely concentrated at the center point of the event horizon. This type of probability distribution can also be interpreted as a density distribution, a result that would surely be accepted by Mr. Louis Victor de Broglie.

From the above description, I propose the following hypothesis:

When used appropriately, the uncertainty principle can avoid an extreme value calculation (e.g. singular calculations), similar to its explanations for the third law of thermodynamics.

This is one solution to avoid the extreme value calculation, given by the observer located in our daily world (i.e. the earth). Another solution will be further introduced in following content.

(6) Dark matter and dark energy

Above it was mentioned that under some exceptional circumstances, a system may exist relative to another outer system that differs from ours. Exotic cosmological objects are excellent examples of such circumstances.

Dark matter is obviously revealed only by its gravitational effect. It can be thought as composed of new particles with gravity-effectible mass and ruled by a new force. Gravitationally, dark matter behaves and gathers like normal matter, and the new force counteracts gravity similarly to the electromagnetic force in our world.

In one scenario, the exotic particles converge into

stars or planets revolving around galactic centers, possibly giving rise to intelligent creatures that view our visible world as dark matter that can interact only with their gravity. However, these “dark-matter beings” would detect our relative existence by interpreting the unconventional phenomenon observed in the rotation of the galaxy.

However, if dark matter is really discretely distributed like stars, their gravity should exert a discoverable effect on the observable celestial sphere. As records of such influences are lacking, dark matter probably exists in some other state.

The gravity and supposed new force acting on dark matter particles can be balanced and the particles are continuously distributed throughout galaxies, or beyond the border of some galaxies. Their gravity will affect the galaxy’s rotation, but as they cannot interact with other forces, they will smoothly admit the passage of stars, planets, and other bodies. Therefore, they exist relative to us in a different system.

These above explanations seem self-justified. But the new particle is hard to be found to support it. As gravity commonly interacts with both dark and normal matter. This may imply itself as more special than the other forces. And this kind of particularity will be further explained in following content to provide another more believable explanation.

Dark energy is even more mysterious; however, I doubt that it constitutes a new entity or new energy. It is so widely distributed throughout the whole universe. If something seems to exist everywhere, then in reality it is nowhere. Dark energy probably is something familiar to us, but hidden characteristic of which we had neglected. If something appears to move faster than light, probably it is space itself.

Like quantum theory, general relativity theory is a correct but incomplete theory, at least not general enough. The introducing of cosmic constant already confirms the non-absolutism of curvature. In fact, this constant should also be treated as a relative parameter.

In general relativity theory, the equation of gravity

field is formulated when observer stands in a space with zero curvature. All other spaces possess higher curvature than it. So the universe is only described by Riemannian geometry. We always consider our daily world has zero curvature, but actually it doesn't. It has slight curvature above zero compared with the void in the universe, even if nearly negligible. It's so slight that we always think "parallel straight lines never intersect", this kind of thing would really apply to our daily world, but actually it wouldn't. Only considering our daily world has zero curvature will make us neglect the existence of space with curvature lower than our daily world. This will cause problem when we try to understand something happened there.

The cosmic constant is insufficient because it supposes that factors other than curvature affect space-time, which complicates the situation. It is better to let curvature itself tell what will be shown to us, during the occurrence of an event at a place with lower curvature than ours.

If consider an entirely flat space be with zero curvature, our space will have positive curvature. If consider our space be with zero curvature, we should accept the existence of a negative curvature. When observing a low-curvature place from a high-curvature place, we can imagine drawing a triangle with seemingly straight lines on the surface of an inflated balloon, then deflating the balloon. As the triangle shrinks, its sides curve inward, forming part of a hyperbola. This curve is the straightest possible line in the lower-curvature place, and will be the path chosen by light.

Negative curvature is well known in geometry and optics, but is relatively new to cosmology. Like positively curved space, negatively curved space can also red-shift light. This red shift is consolidated by observations of a cosmological redshift.

From the above descriptions, I conclude the following hypotheses:

The inner nature of dark energy is the accumulated effect of relatively negative curvature among the vast space of galaxies.

The negative curvature acts as a concave lens for light, red-shifting the light with similar mechanism as observed in positive curvature.

Even miniscule redshifts in a nearly flat space can become observable over astronomical distance accumulation (see Fig. 13).

The above case is similar in principle with another one in our daily life (Fig. 14), which is conceived on the principle of equivalence:

Assuming you are driving the black car with $5a$ rightward acceleration; the other white cars are running with $2a$ rightward acceleration. In the view of white cars, you are actually with $5a$ rightward acceleration; however, seemingly with $3a$ rightward acceleration. Meanwhile, in the view of yourself, the white cars are actually with $2a$ rightward acceleration; however, seemingly with $3a$ leftward acceleration.

When doing the equivalent transformation: You are in the black car and keep stationary relative to a $5g$ leftward gravity field; the other white cars are keeping stationary relative to a $2g$ leftward gravity field. In the view of white cars, you are actually in the $5g$ leftward gravity field; however, seemingly in the $3g$ leftward gravity field. Meanwhile, in the view of yourself, the white cars are actually in the $2g$ leftward gravity field; however, seemingly in the $3g$ rightward gravity field.

We can find the seemingly $3g$ rightward gravity field is the source of the gravity generated from the void parts of universe. This situation is really common in our daily world; however, the self-correcting function based on our daily experience can always help us to ignore the seemingly $3a$ leftward acceleration.

The seemingly $3a$ leftward acceleration will cause a relative speed to try to shorten the distance between the black car and the white cars. So does the gravity caused by the seemingly $3g$ rightward gravity field.

If in the traditional logic, the curvature difference between the black car and white cars is $3g$, which can be also explained by the tidal force along the direction of gravity field. However, we can feel the $5g$ leftward gravity field, and can observe the $3g$ rightward gravity field. This will cause the space seem to be stretched,

and cause a larger redshift than our expectation. This is also similar with a tidal effect caused by the sun to the earth.

This case also implies the acceleration and the conventional gravity field not always have the equivalent effect. When observing a lower curvature place in a higher curvature place, these two will have opposite effect. More rigorously, the acceleration will have the equivalent effect with the gravity field (caused by the curvature difference), but not equivalent with the conventional gravity field (caused only by the density of mass).

This case also implies seeming phenomenon and actual phenomenon have discrepancy. There exists a potential inertial reference system to help us do the judgement. This question will be discussed in following content.

Above we provide a qualitative description only. In a detailed calculation, the constant in the gravitational field equation should be replaced with a variable, and a new sub-equation of negative curvature, formulated in an appropriate geometry such as Lobachevskian geometry, should be introduced.

The cosmic constant actually represents the curvature in the place where the observer is located. The value of it represents the curving degree of the space-time in the place.

If only standing in the viewpoint of our daily world (the earth), the constant is a fixed number. If we need to express the phenomena appeared to observers standing in places with different curvatures, the constant should be replaced with other different and fixed numbers. More generally, the constant should be replaced with a sub-equation to describe the curvature in the place wherever the observer is located.

If we want to express how the universe actually is, we need to use a clean version of the gravity field equation, without involvement of some constant. If we want to express how the universe looks like, we need to use the version with constant or sub-equation.

Furthermore, from this case, we can continue the

stepwise deductions:

We always thought the redshift was caused by stars heading away from us in acceleration. Actually it is caused by negative curvature. These two phenomena really resemble with each other, and both have relation with gravity. After rearranging these above concepts: The relative negative curvature causes gravity, which causes redshift, which seemingly is caused by acceleration.

Both positive and negative curvatures will cause gravity. More rigorously, absolute value of curvature difference will cause gravity. This newly deduced gravity can be used to explain the mechanism of dark energy, as well as wherever we need the presence of gravity but without finding the existence of mass.

Just as we discussed above, another explanation for dark matter will be provided. Among the internal part of a galaxy, there also exists innumerable void spaces. They possess nearly zero mass, and provide relative lower (negative) curvature than other spaces around celestial spheres such as stars or planets.

These void parts are the source of gravity that we need to explain the abnormal behavior of the rotating galaxy. There is almost no mass in the void, so there is gravity generated from.

The inner nature of dark matter is the void parts among the vast space in a galaxy.

These void parts will generate gravity, because they have relative negative curvature.

(7) Curvature

This concept is broadly discussed in previous content. In gravitational field equation, it is used to describe how the space-time is curved. But this equation derived from the general relativity theory is not general enough. This equation supposes the observer stands only in the location with zero curvature. In this precondition, it indeed provides accurate forecast for typical cosmic phenomena. Because our daily world have near to zero curvature, the equation will surely keep on providing accurate forecast as long as we stand and observe on the earth.

However, there are two problems of this equation:

1) This equation can't describe what happened in place with lower curvature than ours. This problem has been revealed in the case to explain dark matter and dark energy. Sub-equation describing the negative curvature should be introduced to complement it.

2) This equation may have potential possibility to give inaccurate forecast when the observer is located in a place with significant curvature above zero. This problem need to be further verified in practice. If this equation doesn't have self-rectifying function when used by different observers located in different curvatures, a new sub-equation should also be introduced to describe relative curvature.

Relative curvature means the curving degree of the space-time presented to the observer will not be an absolute state. It will be a variable quantity, relative to the curvature of the place where the observer is located.

When an observer is located in a place with lower curvature to observe the phenomena happened in a place with higher curvature, the conclusion will be different from what the observer located already in the higher curvature place will get. And vice versa.

When an observer is located in a place with lower curvature to observe the phenomena happened in a place with intermediate curvature, the conclusion will be different from what the observer located in higher curvature place will get. And vice versa (Fig. 15). Suppose the curvature between the lower curvature place and the higher curvature place continuously varies. When we travel between these two points, different observers will give different conclusions. The observer travelling with us, the observer in lower curvature and the observer in higher curvature will consider we are moving along a straight line embedded in a flat surface, in a sphere surface and in a hyperboloid surface respectively.

There is a misconception: We always thought when standing in an elevator with upward acceleration, we would see the light was bended downwards. As the upward acceleration has nearly equal effect with a downward gravity field, we thought the light would be

bended downwards by gravity field as well.

Actually only the result is correct. The light truly will be bended by gravity field. But the deduction process is completely wrong (Fig. 16). As we know, the equivalence principle is only applicable to an infinite small point and its neighborhood, in order to avoid the effect of tidal force. If the small point is really infinite small, there will be no space for the light to be bended to. If its neighborhood be considered to provide any finite small room, the effect of tidal force should be also considered into. Hence, the real situation should be:

In the acceleration case: The light emitted by source outside elevator will seem bended due to the relative motion between source and elevator. Actually even in an elevator rising at a constant speed, we can find the light move downwards.

In the gravity field case: The light emitted by the source in the elevator will be bended by curvature. The same curvature will also cause a small angle (due to the effect of tidal force) between the two internal walls which are originally parallel. The light goes along a bended path and reaches the other side of wall at the same elevation. This is the phenomenon can be observed from the place without gravity field (outside the elevator). And this is the right deduction process for this case.

In the view of the observer in the elevator (in the gravity field), neither the small angle nor the bend will be observed. Because the bended light moves along the shortest path (geodesic) in the curved space-time. The observer will consider the light still goes along a straight path and hits the terminal wall which seems parallel with the wall where the light is emitted.

We can also imagine another source outside the elevator (outside the gravity field) will emit light. The light will not be acted upon by gravity, which means it will spread in the place without gravity field.

In the view of the observer located also in the place without gravity field (outside the elevator), it's just like normal light, moving along a straight line.

In the view of the observer in the elevator (in the gravity field), the light is transmitting in a place with

relative lower curvature. The light will move along a straight line in hyperboloid. This will cause the light seem bended upwards. This bending direction is opposite to the conventional direction of gravity field.

This is really different from our common sense, but this phenomenon is consistent with the mechanism of explaining dark energy. Actually, in this thought experiment the tidal force is not negligible, because the light will move along the horizontal direction. If we take it into consideration, the situation will not be the same with what the equivalence principle described. In other words, the equivalence principle is not applicable to this case.

The above explanation demonstrates the relativity of curvature. Observers always consider they are located in flat space-time regardless of how much the real curvature of their locations are, because the light will always go along the geodesic line in their curved space-time. However, the observers can perceive the differences between their seemingly flat place and the real flat place, due to the different structure of space-time.

From above explanation, we conclude:

Observers located in different curvatures will observe different curving degrees regarding the same curving space-time.

Observers located in different curvatures will give different conclusions regarding the same objects, behaviors, or phenomena.

None of the observations or conclusions is more objective than the others.

Here I will provide another solution for the calculation problem of singularity in the black hole, as mention above. From the previous conclusions, the observer located at a short distance outside the event horizon and still lives will find a different phenomenon. Suppose the real curvature of the observing place is half of that at event horizon. In the view of this observer, the space-time of the event horizon will not be as curved as observed on the earth. If the light here still spreads at the same speed through the shortest path

of this place as the relativity theory told us, apparently the remaining curvature is not sufficient to trap the light to form an event horizon. Instead, a new event horizon seems backed off to the place with a higher curvature far in the distance.

As we move on along the direction of increasing curvature, all the curved space-time seems continuously unfolded and smoothed in front of us, only leaving a seemingly straight path heading to the center of the black hole. Finally when we arrive there, there is no singularity. Only a seemingly flat but actually highly curved observable space-time. This is the solution given by observer located in a relative higher curvature than ours.

From above description, the existence of the black hole is relative. When the observed curvature exceed a certain degree, such as Schwarzschild radius required, the black hole will appear. When the observer moves along the path that cause curvature increase or decrease, the quantity of observed black holes will reduce or increase respectively.

Standing on the earth we will never observe objects moving in or out of a black hole, and never realize what happened inside it. But the observer from other place with much higher curvature may consider there is no black hole, there. At last we should be aware of the fact that due to the different curvature of space-time, conventional substances depending on a spatial structure such as molecular bonds arranged in specific angle may not be available there.

(8) Gravity

This concept is tightly related to the curvature. We always consider gravity derives from the curvature, which is caused by the density of mass. However, the content from previous section provides several different conclusions.

First, not only the mass will cause the curvature, also the void will. Second, the void will provide attraction opposite to the conventional direction of the gravity field. Finally, the observed curving degree depends on the curvature where the observer located.

Combing those conclusions together, we can get the real nature of the gravity:

The gravity is caused by the absolute value of the observed curvature difference.

The direction of gravity will point to the place with curvature difference, not only to the place with high density of mass.

When observing the place with higher curvature than ours, the more density of mass will cause the larger gravity. This kind of gravity is like the conventional gravity presented in our daily world, providing attraction effect pointing to the mass. This kind of gravity will decrease with the increase of distance from mass.

When observing the place with lower curvature than ours, the less density of mass will cause the larger gravity. This kind of gravity is like the mechanism of dark energy, and also provides attraction effect, but pointing to the opposite direction of mass. This kind of gravity will increase with the increase of distance from mass, and looks like an increasing repulsion effect from mass.

Gravity is not the attraction effect between mass. It's actually a geometric effect caused by the distribution of mass. So I really doubt the possibility to find some gravitons.

Furthermore, I would like to discuss two related concepts about gravity.

A) The gravitational mass and the inertial mass:

Assuming a completely rigid object (e.g. a square) formed in lower curvature is put into higher curvature. It will still maintain its original spatial shape, provided the force supporting its spatial structure is stronger than the force caused by the curvature difference. Due to the geodesic line also has a more positive curvature here than in the place where the object is formed, the object will be subject to the effect of bending to a more positive curvature. Meanwhile, in the viewpoint of the observer located in the same higher curvature, this object will become visually bended negatively, for the same reason.

In this case, it's seemingly bended negatively and

actually suffered a positively bending force to prevent the negative bending. The above description resembles with the case that an object is actually accelerated leftwards and seemingly suffers a rightwards inertial force to prevent the leftwards acceleration. The "seemingly" and "actually" in these two cases are interchangeable due to the equivalence principle.

Generally speaking, the acceleration can be caused by the thrust of the electromagnetic force; the maintenance of the spatial structure of an object can be caused by the interatomic and intermolecular forces, which also belongs to the electromagnetic force.

In both cases, the change trend caused by the force generated from the electromagnetic field or from the mass, is being countered by each other. The gravitational mass can provide an inertial force to counter the effect of bending objects to negative curvature caused by the electromagnetic force.

Exactly, in this case, the gravitational mass provide an inertial force.

B) The gravitational field and the electromagnetic field:

From previous explanation of concept, the change trend caused by the force generated from the electromagnetic field or from the mass, is being countered by each other. This is close to interactions between the electric field and the magnetic field. Hence, many researcher intend to unify them, but in vain.

The main problem is that electric charge can be positive or negative, electromagnetic field can provide attraction or repulsion, but gravity seems only provide attraction. Hence, the unifying always brings in the incomprehensible universal repulsion.

In fact, the universal repulsion is reasonable. When we are in a position where the curvature is higher, to observe the position with lower curvature, it is obvious a repulsion force is produced by the mass. Neglecting this kind of repulsion caused by mass is the most critical reason for Mr. Einstein failed to unify them.

These two related concepts about the gravity also

give us an answer about a more fundamental concept: Inertia.

As talked above, the attraction caused by void can also be seemed as a repulsion from mass. This effect will increase with distance increasing. Hence, any object with mass will be under the co-effect of all the mass in the whole universe around you, which can interact with this object. One effect is the attraction, which will decrease while the distance is increasing. The other effect is the repulsion, which will increase while the distance is increasing. This object will be located at a balance position under the co-effect of these two effects.

The repulsion from all places will be quite stronger than the attraction. But the gravity field will interact with every single atom or sub-atom entity in your body, so you will feel nothing about this kind of effect. Meanwhile, you are in the balance position, so the co-effect of these repulsions will be balanced.

When you are acted upon by another kind of force, such as thrust caused by the electromagnetic force, the situation will be (Fig. 17): First, You are in the balance position like in the bottom of the well. Then the thrust will try to push you to a higher place of the well. In that case, the gravity well will provide an opposite effect to you. This opposite effect is caused by gravity, and seemed to be caused by so called inertia.

(9) The inflationary universe and parallel universes

The Inflationary universe can also be comprehended from the relative viewpoint.

At the beginning, the entire universe was squeezed into an extremely small space with extremely high curvature in the view of the latter flatter space. The curvature was delicately maintained by the mass density, which was trapped within by the curvature itself.

When this balance was disturbed by a minor perturbation, the density was lowered by a negligible amount. The consequent reduction in curvature (also to a negligible degree) further reduced the density and flattened the space. Gradually, the universe evolved into its present flat state.

And until now we still believe the inflation is ongoing based the phenomena observed and called as cosmological redshift, which is supposed to be driven by dark energy.

However, from previous conclusions, cosmological redshift is caused by negative curvature. This makes one of the three cornerstones of Big Bang theory seems not solid.

Another cornerstone, cosmic microwave background (CMB), can also be explained by the curvature. When the universe is (or seems) inflating faster than light, this means no light will arrive us. Just as I discussed in the section of dark energy, when the accumulated effect of negative curvature reach a certain amount, it will redshift out all the light from the spectrum, and there will be no light can reach us.

This certain amount can be achieved after a certain distance of accumulation. This distance already have a famous name, the Hubble radius. Since some light can be completely red shifted from the light spectrum, there must be some other light, emitted from the place near to the periphery of the Hubble radius, barely redshifted to the radio wave band when approaching the gravity field of our galaxy. This kind of radio wave will acquire energy while accelerated by gravity and be blueshifted to microwave band when arrives the earth.

The above explanation, can't disprove the Big Bang theory. But it provides another solution for existent phenomena.

No observable material can spread through the space faster than light, but space itself can inflate at ultra-light speed. If the inflation really seems happened, it also can be comprehended from the aspect of curvature.

Parallel universes can also exist within a relative viewpoint. Rather than arising from different conscious choices, parallel universes in this view are some systems that cannot interact with us.

Parallel universes can be composed of different particles ruled by exotic forces that cannot interact with our familiar forces. An entity that completely

exists in a parallel universe would not be recognized by us, because we cannot interact with or observe such entities, but entities in a parallel universe certainly can observe each other.

They can also arise from inflations of universes. During the seemingly inflationary period, objects or systems even if composed with the same kinds of forces may be separated before they can interact with each other. Ultra-light speeds are most likely contributed by the space itself.

In a sense, our seemingly inflationary universe is also one kind of parallel universe. All the interactions from outside of the Hubble radius will be redshifted out from the spectrum. This really resembles with the Schwarzschild radius. All the interactions from inside of the Schwarzschild radius will be redshifted out from the spectrum. In a sense, the black hole is also one kind of parallel universe.

These two distances have one same mechanism: When the effect of curvature difference accumulated to a certain degree, all the information can be isolated and trapped behind the curvature. This kind of isolation will make the isolated part seemingly exists in parallel universe (Fig. 18). The space-time inside any Schwarzschild radius is in the parallel universe of the outside part. And that outside any Hubble radius is in the parallel universe of the inside part. Our universe is only one case among the innumerable cases of them.

Thereafter, how to establish the reference frame to better help us locate in the universe will be discussed.

When talking about principle of equivalence, it is often described as: The observer standing in a uniformly accelerating rocket is equivalent to the observer standing on the surface of a planet. This is widely used in many academic or amateur discussions. However, if we can consider it deeper and ask what does the accelerating mean? What is the compared system when it is accelerating?

To answer this question, Mach Principle is quoted by Einstein. The acceleration is compared with the whole universe. That can explain the acceleration, but imply there is a potentially absolute reference frame, the whole universe. However considering the whole

universe as a reference frame is hard to be judged as absolute or relative. Actually not the whole universe, only the part in the Hubble radius will interact with us, so only this part need to be considered into.

Why the earth, the star system, or even the galaxy can also be treated as inertial system? Because they are all repulsed (attraction also makes some contribution) to a nearly balanced position by the co-effect of all the repulsions and attractions from the related universe. That means the inertial system is not unique. However, once it is established, it can be seemed as absolute. However, this kind of absoluteness is not unique.

Suppose the observer is floating in the outer space where the attraction from earth can be neglected, we can conclude from above content (Fig. 19):

The observer only acted upon by gravity fields can be seemed as in an inertial system.

This inertial system will cover the whole scope in the Hubble radius of this observer.

This observer will be the center (approximately) of this inertial system.

(10) Extended version of Kim et al.'s double-slit experiment

Previously I mentioned an extended double-slit experiment based on version of Kim et al. [14]. This thought experiment was conceived by me as follows. (See Fig. 20).

Suppose that the original experiment is simplified such that the photon can arrive only at detector D1 (or D2) to trigger an interference pattern. Now extend the path between the slits and D1 (or D2) to an adequate distance, and insert a light absorbing plate(s) into the path after emission of photon but before it hits D1 (or D2), to attempt to disable the interference pattern.

Let D , I , and P be the distances between the slits and D_0 , the slits and the inserting point, and the slits and photon when inserting the plate, respectively. These three distances are adjustable, but all should be shorter than the distance between the slits and the mirror M_a (or M_b).

Assuming the left side among the three letters represent the shorter distance, we have six combinations of the above variables, DPI, PDI, PID, DIP, IDP and IPD, and attempt to predict the results in each scenario. All below predictions are based upon previous conclusions that causality is transmitted instantaneously, so the photon and its twin know all the information happened or will happen in the whole optical path.

DPI: In this version, an interference pattern will appear at D_0 , D_1 (or D_2) will not be triggered, and one point will appear on the inserted plate.

The appearing interference pattern is reasonable. If not, it will lead to a terrifying fact that we can predict change (to insert plate) in future. However, feeling terrified is not the cause for the pattern. The cause is that the appearing pattern only tells the prediction of future-before-inserting, which is that photon will arrive at D_1 (or D_2), via an unidentified path. When its twin photons meet at D_0 , in their view it is the future and they will interfere at D_0 to show this future, regardless of whether it will be changed or not. After the plate is inserted, the prediction for future-after-inserting is that the photon will hit the plate, which can only be predicted by increasing D_0 .

This result demonstrates that a photon can forecast its future path in the absence of any new changes. If no change arises, the future is perfectly forecasted. If a change intervenes, the future will deviate from the forecast.

PDI: In this version, no interference pattern will appear at D_0 , D_1 (or D_2) will not be triggered, and a single point will appear on the inserted plate.

This scenario includes an extended D_0 as mentioned in the DPI version. When twin photons arrive at D_0 , the prediction for future is that the photon will be blocked by the plate, which clearly presents “which-way” information, and no interference pattern appears.

This mechanism of this result is that of the previous DPI version.

PID: In this version, no interference pattern appears

at D_0 , D_1 (or D_2) is not triggered, and a single point appears on the inserted plate.

This result is easily explained; the photon is blocked before its twin arrives at D_0 .

DIP: In this version, an interference pattern appears at D_0 , D_1 (or D_2) is triggered, and no point appears on the inserted plate.

IDP: In this version, an interference pattern appears at D_0 , D_1 (or D_2) is triggered, and no point appears on the inserted plate.

IPD: In this version, an interference pattern appears at D_0 , D_1 (or D_2) is triggered, and no point appears on the inserted plate.

These three versions were set as control groups to eliminate any unexpected quantum behavior.

From the above thought experiment and its results, we conclude that:

In the absence of an intervening change, the future is definite; otherwise, the future will be changed. If multiple changes intervene before future arrives, the future outcome will depend on the cumulative effect of each change (see Fig. 21). The cumulating sequence depends upon their occurring order.

If this kind thought experiment could really be done in real world, it would be helpful.

(11) Future

In the previous thought experiment, we considered that the future is definite provided that no new changes result from decisions. Future is like a movie constructed from numerous frames. The content is written in advance, but is only revealed to us frame by frame.

When a new decision is made, a new causality is transmitted everywhere in zero time, but only revealed to us at light speed. Each different decision leads to a definite future. And these futures are superposed in order of their occurrence. The superposed future can be finally observed and confirmed once it is revealed. If one decision is made with definite choice, the future will be definite, and seems definite to us before it is

revealed. If one decision is made with indefinite choices, these indefinite choices can also cause a superposition of future, just like different decisions with definite choice made at the same time. The superposed future will also be definite, but seems indefinite to us until it is revealed. These decisions can be made by human consciousness or quantum processes.

In summary, continual decisions made in the present, based on confirmed results from the past, realize a relatively static and ever-changing future.

We are remembering the past but not forgetting the future, probably because the process of forming memories is in the positive direction arrow of the second law of Thermodynamics.

(12) Noether's theorem [18]

In the previous section, we considered the future as a movie composed of numerous frames. Here we must ask: what dynamic drives objects through the frames, or moves the future towards us? To better explain it, Noether's theorem will be quoted.

Noether's theorem is quite general; however, we limit our discussion to two typical cases: (1) conservation of momentum and symmetry of space translation, and (2) conservation of energy and symmetry of time translation. A visual demonstration is presented in Fig. 22.

In the first case: When a force acts upon a physical system, its effect accumulates into an initial momentum after a period of action time. After the force is removed, the initial momentum remains unchanged and the effect of initial momentum continues accumulating as the system travels in the direction imparted by the force. The initial momentum corresponds to conservation of momentum. The accumulated effect of initial momentum corresponds to symmetry of space translation.

Because after the initial force is removed, in the absence of any other influence, the momentum will remain unchanged. Furthermore, when not acted upon

by a force, the system is inertial; and therefore, whether the spatial translation happened cannot be identified by itself.

More generally, when a force acts upon a physical system, its effect accumulates into an initial state after a certain action range in a certain direction. After the force is removed, the initial state remains unchanged and the effect of initial state continues accumulating as the system travels in the in the direction imparted by the force. The initial state corresponds to the conservation quantity. The accumulated effect of the initial state corresponds to the symmetric quantity.

The concept of force can be generalized to torque, pressure, and other similar physical quantities. In these cases, more conservation quantities and symmetry quantities can be verified. This generalization property is also useful for predicting non-commutability in physical variables.

In the second case: When a force acts upon a physical system, its effect accumulates into an initial energy after a span of action distance (or space). After the force is removed, the initial energy remains unchanged and the effect of initial energy continues accumulating as the system travels in the direction imparted by the force. The initial energy corresponds to conservation of energy. The accumulated effect of initial energy corresponds to symmetry of time translation.

If we consider the force only as some macroscopic propulsive force, the energy only as kinetic energy, the time only as moving time and the distant only as moving distant, it will perfectly answer how one object is moving in frames of time.

An analogous argument can be applied to the four fundamental forces that govern the behavior of our world. Although not all of these forces satisfy the conservation and symmetry relation, the analogy elucidates how forces drive objects and systems in the time direction. That is, we can understand how every object evolves in time.

One typical case is the mass–energy equivalence: the energy carried by a particle is the product of its

mass and the square of the speed of light. Once a particle is formed from the acquired energy, its clock begins to tick and the effect of energy will force particle moving along the time direction until its lifetime ends.

From the above description, we conclude that:

The effect of a generalized force accumulated over generalized space forms a generalized energy. Irrespective of whether aforesaid force is continued or discontinued, the effect of aforesaid energy accumulates over aforesaid space. Consequently, objects acted by aforesaid force are pushed to continue moving in the time direction.

(13) Principle of least action [19]

The above description indicates what makes the future move toward us, but does not elucidate how it moves. Actually, a nearly perfect answer is already provided by the principle of least action. One of its special case is to explain the refraction of light, selecting the soonest way, between two points.

But we still need to ask further: How can the principle of least action know the soonest way to the terminal point before actually arrive there? To answer this question, the path from the starting point to the terminus is already fixed. Because causality is transmitted instantaneously, just after the particle or object departs from start point, the terminal is already there. When time is driven by a certain amount of energy and the future moves toward us at light speed, if different paths can be chosen, a shorter path means a shorter arrival time. So the fastest path is the first path that reaches the present. Other choices will not be revealed. (See Fig. 23). This is the more fundamental reason for principle of least action

This process is similar with previous content. The fastest path provides adequate information, dispelling all other uncertainties.

The above description implies that: With the action of force, the starting point and terminal point are instantaneously fixed in space-time. The soonest path

between them will be chosen to reveal to us, at light speed.

(14) Probability

We now arrive at a crucial question: Why does quantum behavior show probability? How is the result determined? Does any potential factor influence a quantum choice?

First, the fastest path will reach us from the future (as discussed above). In some special cases, such as lens imaging or ping-pong ball between two poles (see Fig. 24), multiple paths will be the fastest. When the fastest way is non-unique, all the possible paths reach us with a certain probability. And the sum of these probabilities will be equal to one.

Second, creating two or more identical choices (fastest paths) in practice is almost impossible. Subtly minor differences among choices can lead to different outcomes. Even in a vacuum, choices are influenced by quantum fluctuations. The minor differences can be the reason to choose different choices.

However, if we really can find some method to create exactly identical condition for choices, and let quantum system to choose, it's not surprising for them to choose any one of them. Because they are exactly the same, choosing anyone is reasonable. They will have the same probability to be chosen.

Finally, the potential factor is curvature, which should be comprehended as a generalized conception. Curvature can be artificially created to establish non-unique fastest paths such as double-slit experiment. Or naturally formed such as atomic orbitals. They have similar mechanism, to create separate choices, but all in soonest path. Furthermore, a pervasive curvature caused by gravity and continuously distributing over all space-time, also counts.

A fundamental reason for the existence of quantum probability should be derived from curvature. In terms of quantum probability, never absolute zero curvature can be achieved, so there always exists probability.

(15) Truth

This is the truth we are pursuing:

The causality will be transmitted instantaneously and prefix the result into the space-time, but the effect will be revealed to other observers only at light speed.

The soonest path to the result will be chosen to demonstrate as the confirmed process, and all the other paths will be dispelled.

When the soonest path is non-unique, all the possible paths will reach us with a certain probability, and the sum of these probabilities will be equal to one.

Relative motion or different curvature will affect the path length between results and observer, which may change occurring sequences of these results and may consequently change the observed phenomena composed by these results.

Different information quantities will affect the path certainty and cause uncertain processes, which may remain uncertain or be confirmed after the result is revealed, depending on whether the interactions between processes occurred or not.

4. Application directions

The following applications of quantum physics are currently under development.

- (1) Quantum computers
- (2) Quantum communication
- (3) Quantum invisibility
- (4) Quantum intelligence
- (5) Other applications

The first two applications are more commonly reported than the others. Their efficacy is mainly restricted by capability, accuracy, and anti-decoherence ability. Proposed methods can be enhancing the capability by using multiple energy-level systems, or verifying their accuracy on parallel quantum computing-systems. Coherent states can be maintained by suitable operations or by only limited observations before the final observation. It is also hoped that the contents of the present article will contribute to these developments.

Quantum invisibility and quantum intelligence have been less exposed to us in terms of their studies.

I propose a previously unreported method for quantum invisibility based on the double-split experiment. A special type of thin film can be fabricated from several layers. The first layer is punctured with densely arranged micro-holes of a preset size and separation, which will admit photons in electromagnetic waves of certain wavelengths to go through like wave. Unlike slits, holes allow omnidirectional diffraction.

The number of holes in the first layer is quadrupled in the second layer. Every four holes in the second layer form the corners of a square centered at one hole in the first layer. More layers can be added by the same mechanism.

The proposed material exploits the properties of electromagnetic waves. When a wave divides into multiple paths, its energy will split into multiple parts, extending the wavelength sufficiently to move around the object behind the film, where they will go on spreading without reflecting the information of the object.

Most of the works on quantum intelligence have focused on quantum computing ability rather than thinking ability. As elaborated above, there are many similarities between quantum mechanics and human consciousness. It appears that quantum intelligence can simulate the mechanism of human consciousness.

The double-slit experiment augmented by detectors, actuators, and a controller provides a good model of quantum intelligence. First, the particles can freely choose one of the slits, and the chosen slit (representing one choice) can be confirmed by observation. The signal sent from the detector to the controller depends on the slit chosen by the particle. For instance, if the particle passes through the left slit, this information is observed by the left detector and sent to the controller. The controller sends a signal to the actuator of a robot, and the robot raises its left hand.

A feedback mechanism can also be established. Modern artificial intelligence can easily identify the

expressions and actions of humans. Moreover, a simple electrical signal by pressing a button can also inform the robot whether its previous behavior (raising its left hand) is commendable or inappropriate.

If the feedback signal is affirmative, the actuator slightly turns the laser transmitter toward the left slit. This action slightly increases the probability of choosing the left slit in the next decision-making step. Maintaining a stationary laser and moving the slits will obtain the same result.

Increasing the number of slits will enable multiple choices. Moreover, multiple systems operated by the same mechanism can be combined into a more complicated system. Although this decision mechanism is less accurate than classical decision making, it mimics the unpredictability of human choosing, which is needed in some special cases.

5. Summary

The following insights were gained from this study.

Wave–particle duality provides only a surface demonstration of certainty. The non-locality hidden in special relativity theory can explain weird quantum behaviors. Dark energy and dark matter both are the relatively negative curvature in our universe. Gravity and inertia are found to be different appearances of one same nature. Principle of least action has a more fundamental reason to determine the path. Quantum probability derives from curvature. A series of other doubts related to quantum theory or relativity theory can be reasonably answered by stepwise deductions.

However, the present contents didn't explain quantum systems with accelerated frames of reference, or quantum systems acted upon by gravity in detail. This article temporally assumes that invariance is not violated in non-inertial systems or gravitational fields. Moreover, after stepwise deductions the inner nature of time, inertia and other fundamental concepts seems emerging, but still needs further consideration. In future work, the present ideas will be extended to these scenarios.

Repetitive obtaining and erasing of information between systems can control the uncertainty state, and

repetitive establishing or eliminating interactions between systems can control the coherence state. The most extreme degrees of these states should be induced, and the useful parts only should be retained, while other parts will disappear at the time of certain state returns.

In this way, we can fully exploit the benefits of quantum mechanics, and the rights granted by the rules of the Universe.

Finally, thanks to Feynman.

As he already told us “Double-slit experiment, has in it the heart of quantum mechanics, contains the only mystery of quantum mechanics.”

Yes, it really does.

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Figure Legends

Fig. 1 Different interaction forms to achieve observation

Fig. 2 A relative description on concept of existence

Fig. 3 Demonstration of wave–particle duality in the individual particle version

Fig. 4 With insufficient input data, the output being vague and uncertain

Fig. 5 The slit through which a particle passes cannot be detected in the “Which-way” version

Fig. 6 Different viewpoints between a human observer and the particle observer in the double-slit experiment

Fig. 7 Setup of a delayed choice version (A and B are the splitters, M1 and M2 are mirrors, and R₁ and R₂ are the receivers).

Fig. 8 Description upon the phenomenon of quantum eraser version

Fig. 9 Description upon the mechanism of quantum eraser version

Fig. 10 Interpretation of the weak measurement version

Fig. 11 Setup of the double-split experiment of Kim et al version (D0, D1, D2, D3 and D4 are detectors, Ma and Mb are mirrors, and Sa, Sb and Sc are splitters).

Fig. 12. Demonstration of entanglement thought experiment

Fig. 13 Cumulative effect of negative curvature over astronomical distances

Fig. 14 Analogy of the gravity produced by negative curvature

Fig. 15 Different conclusions given by observers

located in places with different curvatures

Fig. 16 Thought experiment to contrast the acceleration and the gravity

Fig. 17 The demonstration of inertia

Fig. 18 The similarity of the Hubble radius and the Schwarzschild radius

Fig. 19 The demonstration of inertial reference system

Fig. 20 Setup of thought experiment extended from Kim et al.'s double-slit experiment

Fig. 21 Dependency of the future outcome on the cumulative effect of each change

Fig. 22 Visual demonstration of Noether's theorem with relevant deduction from this article

Fig. 23 Illustration of the more fundamental reason for principle of least action

Fig. 24 Demonstration of curvature causing probability